

Security Assurance Cases in the Medical Domain

Supplemental Material

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1 Security Assurance Cases – Example

As an example for an SAC, a partial case for a Raspberry Pi web server is displayed in Figure 1, where the relation between claims, strategies and evidence can be seen. It also shows an instance of a context element which is used to help set the scope for the claim (where the scope can for example consist of product security requirements and standards that need to be complied with).

2 Questionnaire for Maintainability Focus Group

- What is your title at the case company?
- Have you heard of Security Assurance Cases before today?
- How familiar are you with agile work methodologies?
- What work methodology do you primarily use in your team?
- Are there any documents that you use to support your workflow? If so, which ones?
- Which standards or requirements or documents regarding security or safety do you use in your workflow?
- At which stage do you evaluate the security state of the system/product being developed?
- Do you have a suggestion on where in the process a security review would be suitable?

3 Overview of Relevant Roles at the Case Company

As HOOP is developed by a large multinational company, there are highly specific roles in place to fulfill the domain-specific operational needs and business needs, as well as the product development needs of the company. These roles are outlined in Table 1 below, with the role name, and a brief description of the responsibility of the role.

Table 1: Overview of different relevant roles at the case company

Role	Responsibility
IT Project Manager	Agrees the SaMD life Cycle process with PO, DRP, ITQM & SaMDQM, ITPMs and BPM. Responsible for the successful execution of all IT deliverables.
Product Owner (PO)	Ensures the product is developed to meet the business requirements. Owns, defines and prioritizes services/functionality that deliver business value.
SaMD Quality Manager (SaMDQM) Device Quality	Ensures activities that fall under SaMD procedures meet quality requirements and SaMD quality input into the project.

Table 1 continued from previous page

Role	Responsibility
Business Quality Management (BQM) Clinical Quality	Reviews and approves non SaMD validation documentation in accordance with ITQMF. Ensures GCP compliance for validation activities. Provides GCP quality input into the project.
Quality Technical Manager R&D IT (SWQE)	Ensures SaMD quality processes are implemented according to the quality strategy for the project/product
IT Quality Manager (IT QM)	Assures activities that fall under IT procedures meet IT quality requirements. Provides IT quality input into the project.
Device Responsible Person (DRP)	Accountable for ensuring that development activities meet the medical device requirements.
Risk Management Lead (RML)	Responsible for establishment of the Risk Management File and maintenance throughout the development project. Reviews and approves relevant design controls deliverables.
Device Regulatory Lead (DRL)	Provides regulatory guidance and strategy for the development of the SaMD.
End-to-End Service Capability Manager (E2E CSM)	Responsible for developing service and support models for deployment.
Operational Service Manager (OSM)	Service Management for the HOOP service. Plans and manages changes for the system or service. Monitors and manages the support processes.
Business Analyst (BA)	Responsible for developing user requirements and ensuring requirements meet the business needs.
Solution Architect (SA)	Works with the business and BA to understand functional, non-functional and infrastructure requirements. Responsible for high-level design.
Test Lead (TL)	Responsible for creating test scripts and executing UAT and traceability to user requirements. Responsible for reviewing test scripts and executing UAT and traceability to user requirements.
Test Manager (TM)	Responsible and supporting test scripts creation and executing UAT and traceability to user requirements. Responsible and supporting and reviewing test scripts and executing UAT and traceability to user requirement. Responsible for generating final test summary and traceability reports.
Configuration Manager (CM)	Handles the configuration management and updates the System index.
IT/SW Dev Lead (DEV) (Squad Lead)	Responsible for the Software Design, API Specifications, and Software Detail Design Plan. Responsible for code reviews and checklist compliance, unit and integration tests execution and proper traceability.
Patient Safety Medical Device Lead (PSLMD)	Responsible for patient safety input.

Table 1 continued from previous page

Role	Responsibility
IT Release Manager (ITRM)	Responsible for the successful execution of all IT deliverables during the release process. Manages release process for external/internal partners/clients

4 Use Cases of CASCADE in the Medical Domain

The SaMD coordinator created a total of 15 use cases for SAC in the medical domain seen in Table 2. Two more use cases (numbers 16 and 17 in Table 2) were elicited during the second focus group.

Table 2: Overview of identified use cases for SACs

ID	Use Case Description	Category
1	As a Device Regulatory Lead (DRL), I would use top-level SACs to prove to the regulatory agencies that the company has considered all relevant security aspects of the final product, and has enough evidence to claim that it has fulfilled them to meet the Intended Use claims of the medical device.	Compliance
2	As a member of the Risk and Cybersecurity teams, DRP & RML, I would use detailed SAC to prove compliance to the company, and regulatory teams that the project has complied to the company's Risk & Cybersecurity standard operating procedure, ISO 14971 standard, FDA Guidance in addressing patient safety and cybersecurity concerns and show them evidence of my claim of compliance.	Compliance
3	As a member of the compliance team, SaMDQM, BQM, SWQE, ITQ I would use detailed SACs to review and ensure compliance to the company's Risk & Cybersecurity standard operating procedures, ISO 14971 standard, FDA Guidance in addressing patient safety and cybersecurity concerns and document the effectiveness of the QA review.	Compliance
4	As a project manager or RM, I would use SACs to make sure that a project is ready from a security point of view to be closed and shipped to production.	Assessment
5	As a project manager or RM, I would include SACs in my project plan. I would make sure the project has the needed resources and time for creating the case (argumentation, evidence collection, etc).	Planning
6	As a project manager I would use SACs to monitor the progress of my project when it comes to fulfillment of security requirements.	Monitoring
7	As a product owner, I would use SACs to make an assessment of the quality of my product from a security perspective, and make a roadmap for future security development.	Monitoring, Planning
8	As a product owner, responsible for my project's handling threats and vulnerabilities, I would use SACs to evaluate the effect of new threats and vulnerabilities, and evaluate whether a change is needed to the product or product lines.	Planning

Table 2 continued from previous page

ID	Use Case Description
9	As a member of the supplier assessment team, I would include Monitoring SACs as a part of the contracts made with suppliers, in order to have evidence of the fulfillment of security requirements at delivery time, and to track progress during the supplier's development time.
10	As an cybersecurity Subject Matter Expert, SME on a project Planning team, I would use detailed and visual SACs to communicate with the risk owner, and decide how to update the product security in the right way (to know what to do).
11	As a system leader or solution architect on a project, I would Assessment use SACs to make an assessment of the quality of my system from a security perspective, and make a roadmap for future security development.
12	As a software developer responsible for implementing cyber- Reuse security controls on my project, I would use SACs from previous similar projects as a guideline for secure development practices.
13	As a corporate QA owner, I would use SACs during a EU Compliance or FDA inspection if a regulatory issue is raised against the company for security related issues. I would use the SAC to prove that sufficient preventive actions were taken.
14	As a member of the corporate communication team, I would Assessment use SACs as a reference to answer security related questions.
15	As a member of the Patient Safety team, I would use detailed Compliance SACs to prove to the company compliance and effectiveness of addressing any patient safety concerns with respect to cybersecurity threats that have the potential of any patient safety concerns.
16	As a test manager I would use SACs in order to elicit what Planning needs to be tested for a specific software artifact in order to facilitate traceability to user requirements.
17	As a SaMD Quality Manager, I would provide applicable evi- Assessment dence (test cases and test suite results) to claims in the SAC case, in order to increase the quality and argumentative power of the SAC case, which in turn provides an increased ability to argue for the quality of the product.

5 Overlap of CASCADE with Existing Regulation

Post market In the postmarket management document (PMD) [1] there are several requirements stated that directly tie into different parts of CASCADE. Early on, it states that manufacturers are required to have a "cybersecurity vulnerability and management approach" [1] in place. They then proceed to outline the concrete parts required for such an approach. These are as follows:

1. Identification of assets, threats, and vulnerabilities;
2. Assessment of the impact of threats and vulnerabilities on device functionality and end users/patients;
3. Assessment of the likelihood of a threat and of a vulnerability being exploited;
4. Determination of risk levels and suitable mitigation strategies;
5. Assessment of residual risk and risk acceptance criteria.

Fig. 1. A partial example SAC created for Raspberry Pi web server

Looking at the first item there is a clear use case for the white hat block and the black hat block, with a special emphasis on the first level of both, these being, for the white hat block “*asset identification and decomposition*”, and for the black hat block, “*threat scenarios*”. These are, as the names imply, used for identifying and breaking down the assets that compose the system, and stating what the potential threats to these assets are.

When looking at the second, third, fourth and fifth item there is a connection to the resolver block, which handles risk assessment, and what the treatment for a specified risk should be (mitigation, transfer etc.).

The PMD also states a recommendation for manufacturers to perform cybersecurity risk analyses, and as a part of this analysis, the inclusion of threat modeling is proposed. As explained by Mohamad et al. [?], a *Threat Assessment and Remediation Analysis* (TARA) [7] performed using the threat model STRIDE [6], was used to create the black hat block in a case study at Volvo, which indicates that a TARA, like the one proposed by this document, could be expressed in terms of a black hat block in CASCADE.

It also urges manufacturers to perform software validation, taking the form of software testing (such as unit tests, integration tests etc.), in conjunction with the previously mentioned risk analysis. It then proceeds to elaborate on the main purpose of the software validation, this being the assurance that the remediation applied to identified risks was successful. Not only would CASCADE provide a logical approach for displaying these tests and their results through evidence, but it would also allow for the designer of the case to specify the connection between the risks and their specific testing using risk treatment and concrete requirements as an intermediary step.

Premarket The premarket management document (PreMD) [2], contains the same, identical, bullet list (bullet list 5) as the one presented in the PMD and so the same connections that were made between the PMD and CASCADE related to that list can be made for this document as well.

However, something that is stressed in the PreMD that is not brought up in the PMD, is the need for devices to be trustworthy, stating that “Manufacturers should design trustworthy devices and provide documentation to demonstrate the trustworthiness of their devices in premarket review” [2]. CASCADE has the means to provide this documentation, but a prerequisite to this is

Fig. 2. High level overview of findings in the documentation and their overlap with the blocks of CASCADE. Each concrete part of CASCADE has a specific color, and the corresponding finding in each document that relates to that concrete part has the same color.

that the system already needs to be adequately tested and verified, since the role of SAC is to provide documentation that demonstrates what security measures have already been taken. Having performed rigorous testing and risk proofing of a system does not provide trustworthiness itself, unless it can be properly portrayed through proper documentation, validation and argumentation. This is where CASCADE has the ability to create confidence in cybersecurity contributing towards trustworthiness through the case itself, as this conveys all known and relevant (as scoped in terms of “acceptably secure”) cybersecurity measures taken and through the use of “case quality assurance”. “Case quality assurance” is an element to CASCADE that tries to verify that breakdowns made in the case are exhaustive/complete, meaning that all assets, risks, mitigation strategies etc. have been identified and accounted for. It is also used to show that claims with evidence assigned uphold a certain amount of quality. These two aspects serve to create more trustworthiness in the documentation, which in turn helps to provide trustworthiness for the device.

Just as with the PMD, there are several mentions of software validation and why this is necessary, stating reasons such as reasonable assurance of the safety and effectiveness for the system/product in question. However, the PreMD goes a step further than the PMD by outlining specific design implementations that they recommend (for the submission to be approved by FDA).

The kind of specific implementations include:

“Limit access to devices through the authentication of users” [2]

“Verify the integrity of all incoming data” [2]

Fig. 3. Requirements taken from the PMD document by the FDA [2]

Given a concrete list of required implementations (with a base in cybersecurity, like in Figure 3), any potential SAC approach could prove beneficial for demonstrating compliance with these. The list of implementations can first be used together with the context element, to help set the scope of the case, and further aid in defining what the reoccurring ”acceptably secure” means for the case. If this list has been kept in mind during the product creation, then the case can be used to show that these implementations truly have been taken into consideration for all relevant assets.

Finally the PreMD outlines a list of best practice activities, such as password handling and user authentication. Adherence to best practice elements like these that are relevant throughout the company and incorporate several products can be documented in the generic subcase part of CASCADE.

NIST 800-30 The NIST 800-30 guidance document outlines a risk management process that includes identifying security goals for assets, identifying vulnerabilities, and gives examples of concrete attack vectors (such as phishing attacks, DDoS attacks), in conjunction with suggestions on how the severity of attack vectors can be measured. The identification of assets and security goals align with the purpose of the white hat block in CASCADE, and the identification of vulnerabilities and attack vectors has an overlap with the black hat block in CASCADE.

Medical Device Coordination Group 2019-16 The MDCG guidance document [5] contains similar connections to CASCADE as the FDA issued guidance documents. It explicitly points out the usage of risk management system and threat modeling and security verification and validation through testing. There are also a requirement taken from Annex 1 in the same document regarding information security stating that devices incorporating software should be developed using state of the art risk management and verification. Along with this they provide a definition from ENISA for the information security domain “Protection against the threat of theft, deletion or alteration of stored or transmitted data within a cyber system”. This definition ties in to all parts of CIA and through extension the security goals in the white hat block.

However, the MDCG also includes a statement that urges healthcare providers to learn and adhere to best practices when it comes to general cybersecurity measures. A list from the MDCG document [5] of what is meant by best practices is specified in the list below:

1. Good physical security to prevent unauthorised physical access to medical device or network access points.
2. Access control measures (e.g. role based) to ensure only authenticated and authorised personnel are allowed access to network elements, stored information, services and applications.
3. Network access controls, such as segmentation, to limit medical device communication.
4. General patch management practices that ensure timely security patch updates.
5. Malware protection to prevent unauthorised code execution;
6. Security awareness training.
7. Auditability that supports non-repudiation, i.e. the ability to reliability determine who made what changes to the system and when to assist with forensics.

Viewing these from the perspective of CASCADE, a strong connection can be made between the implementation of these, and the block of CASCADE known as the ”generic sub case”. As the main purpose of the generic sub case is to abstract and document general practices and standard

operating procedures that are prevalent at the entity in question (such as a pharmaceutical company), that in turn lead to an improved security at the entity. The incorporation and conformity of the above mentioned items would be displayed in the generic sub case. This is due to all of them relating to general non-product/system specific practices (or practices that span over for example a family of products).

In the MDCG guidance document, there is also a section dedicated to how documentation should be handled. In this section it specifically states that documentation should conform with the requirements stated in “Medical devices regulations, Annex I”. Showing that conformity has been achieved given specific regulations is one of the key features of a SAC approach, and as explained earlier having concrete requirements are crucial for scoping the case (which is immensely important when the main focus is demonstrating compliance or conformance to specific requirements, as SACs in general have a tendency to grow very large when the scope is large). Looking closer at Annex I [5], there are requirements that regard risk and impact assessment, security awareness training and data integrity that would be part of the resolver block, generic sub case and white hat block in that order.

Fig. 4. Mapping between important areas introduced in MDCG Annex I and CASCADE blocks

Good Clinical Practice (GCP) In response to an enquiry made to the European Medicines Agency, regarding the cybersecurity requirements imposed by the GCP quality standard, the response outlined important sections of the “Guideline on computerised systems and electronic data in clinical trials”.

It mentions an array of best-practices for a good cybersecurity posture, including the use of data backups, network firewalls, anti-virus software and authentication policies. At one point the sentence “There should be documented training on the importance of security” is used. Showing conformance with best practice requirements like these can be achieved through the generic sub case. The best practices present in the document are motivated through threat scenarios/attacks that could occur if the implementation of the best practices is not successful.

It further stresses the importance of data integrity, as any unauthorized or uncontrolled changes to the data can jeopardize the results of the clinical trial, as well as impact the privacy and integrity of the participants in the clinical trial. This property is something that could be shown through the white hat block (through security goals, i.e the integrity is not compromised).

ISO 14971 A central piece to the ISO 14971 [4] is an artefact called the “risk management file”. The way this file is specified ties into several of CASCADEs usage areas. The specification consists of a risk analysis defined as documentation of intended usage and foreseeable misuse, identification of safety related characteristics and identification of hazards.

Certain safety related characteristics can then be expressed in the white hat block, such as properties that need to be preserved (security goals) in order to prevent hazardous situations, namely security risks with properties that could have a safety impact. There are also safety related characteristics that can be expressed in the black hat block, but then of the kind that relates to the concrete situations that could potentially result in a violation of the established properties that

need to be preserved (threat scenarios). However, there are some safety related characteristics that have no connection to cybersecurity (such as short-circuits or battery damage) that do not belong in a SAC.

Risk control is indirectly performed through assigning risk treatments in the resolver block and then providing evidence, that ensures that the risk has reached an acceptable level. In regards to the requirement of providing traceability between risks and the “risk management process”, it is one of the core functionalities of CASCADE and any other SAC approach, as they are explicitly tied together in the assurance case. The same reasoning goes for using the risk management file as a way to show compliance during an inspection.

The document also stresses the importance for completeness when doing risk management as “An incomplete task can mean that an identified hazard is not controlled and harm can be the consequence.” CASCADE tries to control for this by utilising quality claims that involves gathering evidence that all risks/hazards have been accounted for, and argues for the achieved completeness. It further calls for the identification of characteristics related to safety, as well as identification of hazards, which are tied to the identification of assets that the medical device consists of.

There are also mentions the requirement of competence of the personnel responsible for carrying out the risk management process and application of ISO 14971, and that they have the necessary skills, education, training and experience of the applicable medical device, as well of the technologies and the risk management techniques used during the risk management process. These properties tie in to the “Generic Sub Case” of CASCADE, and that there are skills and practices in place that carry over between different (separate) applications of SAC creation using CASCADE.

A noteworthy statement that ISO 14971 makes is that the standard can be used to assess all types of risks that are related to medical devices, not only cybersecurity related ones. As CASCADE is a SAC approach, only cybersecurity based risks are to be recorded in the case, meaning that purely safety based risks need to be handled with another process (such as FTA and SAAC).

ISO 62304 As ISO 62304 requires that a risk management process is applied in accordance with the specifications in ISO 14971 “The **MANUFACTURER** shall apply a **RISK MANAGEMENT PROCESS** complying with ISO 14971.”, the same connections to CASCADE that was made for that standard in regards to the risk management process can be made for ISO 62304 as well.

The ISO 62304 standard also requires that documentation providing traceability be created, the sought after traceability is described as: hazardous situation -> software item -> software cause -> risk control measure -> verification of measure (as shown in Figure 5). This way of showing traceability is almost identical to the flow in CASCADE going from an asset (software item) in the white hat block, through the other blocks, to finally reach a level where evidence is provided.

Fig. 5. Outline of risk management process flow in ISO 62304 [3]

Fig. 6. Excerpt of the SAC created for the HOOP system.

6 Security-Assurance Case for the HOOP System

Figure 6 shows an excerpt from the benchmark case created for the HOOP system. The arguments and evidence shown in the figure are taken from the resolver and evidence CASCADE blocks. The example in the figure can help test managers in use case (16) to assess if there is sufficient evidence to justify the claims in the requirements level of the resolver block, e.g., by examining the case quality evidence claims CQE:25.1 and CQE:25.2.

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